

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND SELF-CONCEPT AMONG ADOLESCENTS

Vijay Kumar¹

Present study intends to study the relationship of emotional intelligence and self-concept among XI class student. A Correlational design was applied on the Self-concept and Emotional Intelligence scores of senior secondary school students. A sample of 226 students was selected through purposive sampling technique from senior secondary schools selected randomly from Patiala district affiliated to CBSE. The tools used in the study are Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII) by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Dr. (Mrs.) Shubhra Manga & Self concept questionnaire (SCQ) by Dr. Raj Kumar Sarswat. Karl Pearson's product moment correlation technique was used to analyse the data. The results of the study indicated that emotional intelligence and self concept are positively correlated with each other. Also, emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept i.e. 'physical', 'social', 'temperamental', 'educational' and 'intellectual' are also found to be correlated. The implication of the study is that the institutions must provide proper environment for development of self concept.

1. INTRODUCTION

In view of the tremendous rate at which change is taking place in the diverse spheres of human life and which is likely to accelerate in the present century, we need a vision to equip ourselves to meet the emerging challenges.

Education makes an attempt to develop man in terms of his multidimensional personality and behind this object there must be some aim because education is an ethical activity, it is unthinkable without aims, so in order to achieve one's aim one should have glorious academic record. The overall process of education of development of man involves academic achievement also. National Policy on Education (1986) highlighted the erosion of values and has brought the focus to redesign the curriculum to make education a forceful tool for the inculcating social and moral values. If the goal of education is quality, it cannot be achieved without the sincere efforts of dedicated and committed teacher.

1.1. Self-Concept

In recent times, the importance of self-concept has been increasingly talked upon in understanding of human behavior. Without knowing self, understanding of human behavior is incomplete and inaccurate.

Individual's self-concept is considered as one of the most basic and crucial component of personality. The formation of self-concept is fundamental to the

¹ Associate Professor & COD, Department of Education, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, India, E-mail: vijay. chechi@lpu.co.in

development of the individual's personality. Self-concept, as the name implies, is one's concept about oneself. As an individual grows, he not only forms concepts about his surroundings and other individuals, but also gradually forms an image or concept of himself. It is his own conception of intelligence, abilities, academic achievement, mental health, temperamental qualities, emotional tendencies, behavior and socio-economic status. The self-concept is the apex of all the social and personal experience the child has had.

The interaction between the individual and his total environment forms an image of his own self. He begins to realize his health, structure of the body, and his potentialities. Then he rates himself as high or low. This concept may be positive or negative. If the individual gradually becomes conscious of his superiority, his self-concept may be positive, but if he feels neglected and insecure he develops a negative self-image.

Self-concept is referred by Lowe (1961) as one's attitude towards self. Sarswat and Gaur (1981) define self-concept as the individual's outlook about himself and his way of thinking, feeling and behaving.

Self-concept is built of two forces: the inherited capacities and environmental pressure. In the beginning, the human child craves for personal contact, love and fondling, which if satisfied leads to healthy and normal growth. Parental acceptance and warmth experience by the child is quite positively related to ego, super ego, and better self-image. If the child receives adequate care, cuddling attention, he would look upon other people as a source of gratification and would consider the world as a safe and interesting place to live.

Basavana (1971) conducted a study to investigate self-confidence as an attribute of self-concept. The study was conducted on 300 college students and it was found that individuals who had high self-concept had higher general mental ability and self-confidence. Sharma (1978) conducted a study on 1427 students (690 males, 737 females) and found that self-concept showed high positive relation with intelligence and self-concept of boys was higher than that of girls. Gupta (1984) concluded that studied that self-concept, anxiety, dependency and adjustment are somewhat correlated to each other in the experimental group. However, self-concept and adjustment are found to be positively correlated, however, self-concept and anxiety are negatively correlated. However, aggression is not found to be correlated with achievement motivation, self-concept & academic and non-academic achievement (Srivastava, 1988). But, curvilinear correlation was reported of aggression with self-concept, & academic and non-academic achievement.

Self concept has been studied with different variables, although the emotional intelligence which is important in day to day functioning of individuals has not been studied. How much emotional intelligence will be instrumental in developing self concept needed to be studied?

1.2. Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence becomes a popular phrase in recent times. Emotional Intelligence affects our life every single day. It appears to be an important set up of psychological abilities that relate to life, the measurement of which is necessary for help and guidance to the needed ones and for self help.

Emotional Intelligence is comprised of two words – ‘Emotion’ and ‘Intelligence’. The term emotional intelligence was coined by two American University Professors Mayer and Solovey (1993) in their attempt to develop a scientific measure for knowing the differences in people’s ability in areas of emotions. Emotional intelligence according to Mayer and Solovey is the ability to monitor one’s own feelings and emotions to discriminate among them; and to use this awareness of emotions to guide one’s thinking and action.

The capacity of recognizing one’s own feelings and that of others for motivating oneself and for managing emotions well in our relationships is termed. There are however two major conceptualizations of emotional intelligence. The ability models focused upon the inter play of emotions and intelligence, however, the mixed models explained a composite conception of intelligence, that includes mental abilities and other dispositions and traits (Bar-on, 1997; Goleman 1995).

Emotional intelligence is a four step process which includes: 1) to perceive emotions, 2) To integrate emotions, 3) To understand emotions, 4) To manage emotions. Emotional intelligence enables individuals to take action appropriately to different kind of environmental situations and help him to gain insight and plan right behavior in work, family and social settings. Emotional intelligence helps human beings to understand emotions; & prescribes preventive measures against bad behaviour anxiety, frustration, boredom and depressions etc.

The teacher has to deal with the young minds to generate new knowledge. Different studies have pointed out the role of emotional intelligence in developing teacher effectiveness. Positive relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher effectiveness have been reported on junior college teachers (Das and Behera, 2004); among University Lecturers (Hassan et al, 2015); nursing faculty (Allen *et al.*, 2012).

Chan (2005) reported that male and female do not differ on the self-perceptions of individuals. It is further reported that family hardiness and emotional intelligence are collectively able to predict self-perceived creativity.

Manhas and Gakhar (2006) found positive correlation between independent variables of general intelligence and emotional intelligence. Also adolescents creativity was positively and significantly correlated with their emotional intelligence and significant positive relation between academic achievement and emotional intelligence.

Sy *et al.* (2006) found that both job satisfaction and performance are positively correlated with emotional intelligence among employees. Also, positive relationship

was found between manager's emotional intelligence and job satisfaction among employees with low emotional intelligence than employees with high emotional intelligence.

1.3. Significance of the Study

As the result of study of behavioral sciences we have come to know, how and why people react, in varied socio-economic, cultural, psychologically and emotionally complex situations. Every body has his own self-concept due to which individual differences exist. As a result there are different adjustments as well as academic problems. Self-concept develops different potentialities in different social, economic, psychological and educational, backgrounds and accordingly are formed their self-concepts. Studies have found that students who form weak self-concepts show weak academic performance and adjustment to different social situations than one's that form strong self-concepts. In the same way, in the present times at work environment, emotional intelligence is being regarded as a major factor of one's success. Self-concept and emotional intelligence which are relatively new concepts of psychology, requires a lot of exploration. There is a significant dearth of research material on all these variables. Self-concept and emotional intelligence affects the dimensions of one's personality, behavior and academic achievement, but their relationship remains unstudied yet. Self-concept directs one's behavior of influencing one's thoughts, feelings and actions.

Schools are instrumental in nurturing a child into polished, nourished and chiseled individual with all round developed personality. It is a fact that proper environment for nurturing in success in academic field develops self-esteem and self-confidence among children. Good role played by schools leads to development of professionals which are well adjusted in society. Emotional intelligence can be potentially useful in understanding and predicting student's performance in various activities as well as co-curricular activities. The present study intends to bring into focus the relationship between self-concept and emotional intelligence. It will help us to know the usefulness of this concept and channelizing the student's potential, abilities, and capabilities in desired direction. Further, it will highlight the importance of these constructs for better functioning of society.

1.4. Objective of the Study

The present study endeavors to study the relationship between self-concept and emotional intelligence among XI class student.

1.5. Hypothesis

In order to realize the objective, it has been hypothesised that there exists no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept for various sub groups i.e. total students; high achievers; low achievers; boys;

girls; high achiever boys; high achiever girls; low achiever girls; & low achiever boys.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Design of the Study

A Correlational design was applied on the Self-concept and Emotional Intelligence scores of senior secondary school students.

2.2. Procedure

For the present study a sample of 226 students were selected through purposive sampling technique from senior secondary schools selected randomly from Patiala district affiliated to CBSE. To the selected sample, Self-concept questionnaire and emotional intelligence inventory were administered to get self-concept and emotional intelligence scores. Also, the marks obtained in X class board examination was taken as academic achievement scores. After the collection of data, the academic achievement scores of the students were put in descending order. The range of the academic achievement scores of the students was from 518-243. For finding high and low achievers .30 and .70 percentiles were calculated, the scores at .30 and .70 percentile were 392 and 450 respectively. The students having marks below 392 and above 450 were assigned as low and high achievers. After this the data obtained was subjected to statistical analysis.

2.3. Tools

The following tools have been administered to conduct the present study:

1. Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII) by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Dr. (Mrs.) Shubhra Mangal.
2. Self concept questionnaire (SCQ) by Dr. Raj Kumar Sarswat.

2.4. Statistical Technique

Karl Pearson's product moment correlation was employed to find interrelationship between Emotional Intelligence and various dimensions of Self Concept for various sub groups i.e. total students; high achievers; low achievers; boys; girls; high achiever boys; high achiever girls; low achiever girls; & low achiever boys.

3. RESULTS

The bi-variate relationship between the emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept scores are calculated and are shown below in the table 1.

TABLE 1: CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND VARIOUS DIMENSIONS OF SELF CONCEPT

Emotional Intelligence	Dimensions of self-concept	'r' value				
		Total	high achievers	low achievers	Boys	Girls
		N=170	N=86	N=84	N=84	N=86
	Physical	0.196 *	0.098	0.319 **	0.2096	0.1918
	Social	0.238 **	0.244 *	0.201	0.2367	0.2393 *
	Temperamental	0.36 **	0.243 *	0.356 **	0.4153 **	0.2848**
	Educational	0.214 **	-0.0036	0.279	0.216	0.2102
	Moral	0.0238	0.0495	-0.053	0.0456	-0.0082
	Intellectual	0.170 *	0.1092	0.202	0.1618	0.1788
	Total self-concept	0.297 **	0.1917	0.314 *	0.3052 **	0.2857**
	Dimensions of self-concept	high achiever boys	high achiever Girls	low achiever girls	low achiever Boys	
		N=24	N=62	N= 24	N=60	
	Physical	-0.14	0.2327	0.0655	0.3699 **	
	Social	0.0699	0.3096 *	-0.0214	0.2611 *	
	Temperamental	0.2601	0.2381	0.01306	0.430 **	
	Educational	-0.1396	0.06989	0.0774	0.3057 *	
	Moral	0.1376	-0.00493	-0.0853	-0.0433	
	Intellectual	-0.0938	0.1966	0.1401	0.2254	
	Total self-concept	-0.0062	0.2788 *	0.04768	0.368 **	

** Significant at 0.01 level of confidence

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

Above table 1 shows that the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and self concept has been found to be significant at the 0.01 level. The tabulated value at 168 df, for 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.151 and 0.198 respectively. The 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept i.e. 'physical', 'social', 'temperamental', 'educational' and 'intellectual' are also found to be significant either at the 0.05 or 0.01 level of confidence. This finding is in tune with the previous finding of Burk *et al.* (1975).

Among high achievers group, it has been observed from table 1 that the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept i.e. 'social' and 'temperamental' dimensions is found to be significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. The tabulated value at 84 df, for 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.212 and 0.261 respectively. This finding is in tune with the previous finding of Goswami (1978).

Among low achievers group, it has been observed from table 1 that the 'r' value for correlation between self-concept and emotional intelligence is found significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. Also, the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and 'physical' and 'temperamental' dimensions of self-

concept are found significant at the 0.01 level of confidence. The tabulated value at 82 df, for 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.215 and 0.281 respectively. This finding is in tune with the previous finding of Shanmugasundram (1983).

Among boys, it has been observed from table 1 that the 'r' value for correlation between self-concept and emotional intelligence is found significant at the 0.01 level of confidence. Also, the 'r' value for correlation between 'temperamental' dimension of self-concept and emotional intelligence is found significant at the 0.01 level of confidence. The tabulated value at 82 df, for 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.215 and 0.281 respectively.

Among girls, it has been observed from table 1 that the 'r' value for correlation between self-concept and emotional intelligence is found significant at the 0.01 level of confidence. Also, the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and 'social' and 'temperamental' dimensions of self-concept are found to be significant either at the 0.05 or 0.01 level of confidence. The tabulated value at 84 df, for 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.212 and 0.261 respectively.

Among high achiever boys and low achiever girls, the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept is found to be not significant even at the 0.05 level of confidence.

Among high achiever girls, it has been observed from table 1 that the 'r' value for correlation between self-concept and emotional intelligence is found significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. Also, the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and 'social' dimension of self concept is significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. The tabulated value at 60 df, for entries at 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.250 and 0.325 respectively.

Among low achiever boys, it has been observed from table 1 that the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and self-concept is found significant at the 0.01 level of confidence. Also, the 'r' value for correlation between emotional intelligence and 'physical', 'social', 'temperamental' and 'educational' dimensions of self-concept are found to be significant either at the 0.05 or 0.01 level of confidence. The tabulated value at 58 df, for entries at 0.05 level and 0.01 level by linear interpolation are 0.255 and 0.331 respectively.

Hence the hypothesis namely; there exist no relationship between emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept is rejected except for sub groups i.e. high achiever boys and low achiever girls.

3.1. Conclusion

From the above results, it can be concluded that emotional intelligence and self concept are related to each other. Similarly, emotional intelligence and various dimensions of self-concept i.e. 'physical', 'social', 'temperamental', 'educational'

and 'intellectual' are also found to be correlated. Similar results have been reported by previous studies by **Burk *et al.*, 1975; Goswami, 1978; Deshmukh and Sawalakhe, 2010; Pushpa and Yeshodhara, 2014**. This implies Self Concept and Emotional Intelligence supports each other and help in development of them among adolescents. If an individual has higher Self Concept about him/herself, then he/she will be more able to have knowledge of his abilities, competencies, weaknesses, and limitations. These characteristics are in line with the characteristics of an emotionally intelligent individual. An emotionally intelligent individual is self aware about his own strengths and weaknesses; is able to control both positive and negative emotions; gives his best in different areas of professional practice and activity; are eager, driven and ambitious; are able to empathise with others and help them accordingly; As a result they are more effective in their routine work. Thus, a student with higher self concept will naturally have more self confidence and can develop good emotional intelligence and will be better in dealing with other persons at school i.e. students, teachers and staff & situations in life in a positive way.

References

- Allen, D. E., Ploeg, J., & Kaasalainen, P. (2012). The relationship between emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness in nursing faculty. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 28(4), 231-40, Jul-Aug, 2012. DOI: 10.1016/j.profnurs.2011.11.018.
- Bar-On, R. (1997). *The Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQ-i): Technical manual*. Toronto, Canada: Multi-Health Systems, Inc.
- Basavanna, M. (1971). Studied of Self-Confidence as an Attribute of Self-Concept. Ph.D. Psychology, S.V.University. In *Third Survey of Educational Research*. (1978-83). New Delhi, N.C.E.R.T.
- Chan, D. W. (2005). A study of self-perceived creativity, family hardiness and emotional intelligence of Chinese gifted students in Hong Kong. *Journal of Secondary Gifted Education*, 16 (2-3), p 47-56. Retrieved from <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ698315>.
- Cooper, R. & Sawaf, A. (1997). *Executive EQ*, New York: Orient Books.
- Das, D.N. & Behera, N.P. (2004). Teacher Effectiveness in Relation to Their Emotional Intelligence. *Journal of Indian Education*, II, 51-62, Nov. 2004.
- Deshmukh, N. H. & Sawalakhe, S. P. (2010). Self Concept, Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment of Adults. *Indian Journal of Psychometry and Education*, 41 (2), 181-185.
- Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional Intelligence, Why it can matter more than IQ*. New York: Bantam Books.
- Goswami, P.K. (1978). *A Study of the Self Concept of the Adolescents and its relationship with Scholastic Achievement and Adjustment*. Doctoral Dissertation, Agra University.
- Gupta, J. P. (1984) Self concept, dependency and adjustment pattern of abandoned institutionalized preadolescent. In *Fourth survey of Educational Research*, 1, 369-70, New Delhi, N.C.E.R.T.
- Hassan, N., Jani, S. H. Md., Som, R. M., Hamid, N. Z. A. & Azizam, N. A. (2015). The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness among Lecturers

- at Universiti Teknologi MARA, Puncak Alam, Malaysia. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 5 (1), January 2015.
- Lowe , C. M. (1961). The self-concept: Fact or artifact? *Psychological Bulletin*, 58, 325-336. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/h0048771>.
- Manhas, K.D & Gakhar, S.C (2006). "Non cognitive correlation of Emotional intelligence of adolescents", *Journal of Educational Research and Extensions*, Vol. XXXXIII No.1, pp. 1-9.
- Mayer, J. D. & Salovey, P. (1993). Emotional Intelligence and construction of feelings. *Applied and Preventive Psychology*, 4, 197–208.
- Pushpa & Yeshodhara (2014). Emotional Intelligence and Self Concept of B.Ed Students. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research (IJEPR)*, 3 (2), June 2014. Retrieved from http://ijepr.org/doc/V3_Is2_June14/ij5.pdf.
- Saraswath, R. K. & Gaur, J. S. (1981). Approaches for the measurement of self concept: An introduction. *Indian Educational Review*, 16 (3), 114-119.
- Sharma, K. L. (1978). A comparative study of self-concept of high and low achievement and intelligent groups of students of class X in urban schools of Bareilly. In *Third Survey of Educational Research. (1978-83)*. New Delhi, N.C.E.R.T.
- Srivastava, N. (1988). A study of aggression in adolescent boys and girls in relation to their self-concept, achievement motivation and performance. In *Fifth survey of Educational research*, p 935-936, New Delhi, N.C.E.R.T.
- Sy, T., Tram, S., & O'Hara, L. A. (2006) Relation of employee and manager emotional intelligence to job satisfaction and performance. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 68 (3), p 461-473, Jun 2006. Retrieved from <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ737842>.